

LINGUACULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF “FATHER”
IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS AND SAYINGS.

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Annotatsiya: Ona va ota oddiygina so'z, ibora yoki jumla bo'lib, u orqali inson bo'ladi, u aniqlanadi, chaqiriladi, tavsiflanadi, farqlanadi va tasniflanadi. Yerda va ko'p osmonlarda hech narsa nomsiz mavjud emas. Ona va ota tarix, madaniyat, meros, til va o'z imidji va g'urur ongini etkazadi. Shundan so‘ng, Injildagi ko‘plab iboralar va jumlar ingliz tilida ota-ona haqida xalq tomonidan qabul qilingan bo‘lsa, o‘zbek tilida ota-ona, ota va onaga nisbatan madaniy axloq va hurmatning aksariyati islom qoidalari, hadislar va Qur’oni Karimga asoslanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: maqol, matal, masal, tushincha, tarjima, muqobillik, tahlil.

Annotation: A mother and father is simply a word, phrase or sentence by which a human being is by it, he or she is identified, called, described, distinguished and classified. Nothing on earth and in much of the heavens exists without a name. A mother and father convey history, culture, heritage, language and a consciousness of self-image and pride. Consequently, many sayings and sentences in Bible have been popularly accepted about parents in English while most of the cultural ethics and respect towards parents and father and mother in Uzbek are based on Islamic rules, hadiths and the Holy Qur’an.

Key words: proverb, saying, concept, translation, alternatives, analysis.

Аннотация: Мать и отец — это просто слово, фраза или предложение, с помощью которых человек идентифицируется, называется, описывается, различается и классифицируется. Ничто на земле и на многих небесах не существует без имени. Мать и отец передают историю, культуру, наследие, язык и сознание собственного образа и гордости. Следовательно, многие

высказывания и предложения в Библии о родителях на английском языке были общеприняты, в то время как большая часть культурной этики и уважения к родителям, отцу и матери на узбекском языке основана на исламских правилах, хадисах и Священном Коране.

Ключевые слова: пословица, поговорка, понятие, перевод, альтернативы, анализ.

The following proverbs and sayings reflect the fact that the Uzbek people have a long tradition of honoring, respecting and honoring their parents, namely, to “father”.

For example, in the stable combination of “Ota rozi - xudo rozi” the level of the father is extremely glorified. In our nation, the fact that children first of all try to get the consent of their fathers is a clear proof of this. Because when you do good to someone or achieve something, of course, they use the saying, “Otangga rahmat”. It is the dream of every father to hear this applause. After all, in our nation, a child is the face of a parent. The Uzbek “Andisha” is also evident in the article "Ota oldidan o'tma, odob oldidan ketma" in english "Do not go before the father, do not go before the manners." Because there are unwritten rules, such as not speaking back to the father, listening to his advice, not speaking harshly, that are ingrained in our blood. The spiritual image of people is often determined by their attitude towards their parents. These, in turn, are directly linked to religious views. As a proof of this, we can cite our hadiths. According to the hadiths, a man "Yo Rasululloh, mening yaxshi muomila qilmog'imga kim haqliroqdir?", deb so'raganlarida Janobi Rasululloh uch marotaba "Onangga" va undan keyin "Otangga", replied. Every nation has always relied on religious and secular knowledge in the upbringing of children. These values have been passed down to the present day through proverbs and sayings, which are directly examples of folklore, and have always existed as the spiritual wealth of the people. For example, the proverb "Onangga boshingni ham qil, Otangga gapingni kam qil", in English "Keep your head to your mother, keep your words to your father" has an educational value and encourages children to be polite and respect their parents. Or we

can see the upbringing in real Uzbek families through the stable combination of "Ota - bilak, ona - yurak" in English "Father - wrist, mother - heart."

Of course, in the family, the father plays a managerial role. He will always be the ideal person for his children. The mother is primarily responsible for their upbringing, instilling in the child a sense of devotion and love for the motherland, as well as a sense of morality. This sentence is expressed in English as follows "Any man can be a father but it takes a special to be a dad". Respect for parents and obedience to their advice are more typical of oriental literature. Of course, it would be wrong to conclude that there is no teaching in Western literature.

There are many examples of respect for parents. For example, "Listen to your father, who gave you life, do not despise your mother when she is old". That is, it means: "Senga hayot in'om etgan otangni so'zlarini tingla, onang qariganda unga g'amxo'rlik qil". The Uzbek version of the article "See your father, come down the horse" is as follows: "Otangizni ko'rsangiz otdan tushing". This proverb is used figuratively to encourage people to honor their father. Similar proverbs and sayings can be found and analyzed in many languages.

The factual paremiological material collected by us is the basis for the division of English and Uzbek folk proverbs into a number of thematic groups. Among them, the thematic group "Father and mother lexeme proverbs" is distinguished by its specific features. The category father and mother lexemes in English and Uzbek proverbs come in a one parema. In some of the paremiological units, the word parents (father and mother) occur as a component of the proverb.

We grouped these proverbs into a separate group.

In the centuries-old culture and pre-determined moral characteristics of the English people, respect for parents is glorified and disregard for them is strongly condemned. The proverb emphasizes this: Honor the father and the mother.

In the centuries-old Uzbek spirituality, the mother is seen as a loving, selfless, self-sacrificing, father is intelligent, head of the family, a breadwinner, parents are as two wings of a bird, and it is both an obligation and a duty for children to respect them.

Wich is pronounced: Onangni quyosh bilsang, otangni oy bil;(If you know your mother the sun, know your father the moon), Otasini og`ritgan el ichida xor bo`lar, onasini og`ritgan parcha nonga zor bo`lar(The one who hurts his father will be oppressed, the one who hurts his mother will be poor), Ona kulsa , xona to`lar, ota kulsa g`aming ketar,(If the mother laughs, the room fills, if the father laughs, the grief disappears).

According to P. Bakirov, “in a number of Uzbek folk proverbs, fathers are intelligent and mothers are kind people: Uzbek: “Ota – aql, ona – idrok”,(Fathers are intelligent, mothers are wise), Uzbek: “Ota – bilak, ona-yurak”,(Father - wrist, mother – heart), Uzbek: “Ona – mehribon, ota – g`amg`usor”, (The mother is kind and the father is sad). Uzbek: “Onalik uyning ori bor, otalik uyning – zari”, (The mother's house has a shame, the father's house has gold). Uzbek: “onang o`ldi-otang o`ldi” (Your mother is dead, your father is dead).

In brief, every work of art reflects the hidden feelings of the people. That is why they are man-made miracles. Therefore, it is determined by the assessment of complex social situations, from a small life event, whether it is a fairy tale, or a parable, or a proverb or a parable. Folklore is also an integral part of fiction. That is why these works are always respected as invaluable values not only of the Uzbek people, but also of the spiritual treasures of other nations.

The followings are taken from the examples of sayings about “father” in English:

- Fathers are the first friend you make and the last love of your life;
- A dad is more than just the sum of his parts. He is the very soul of the family;
- A dad is the anchor upon which his children stand
- Fathers are men who dared to place the world’s hopes and dreams in their children;
- The value of a loving father has no price;
- When a father speaks, may his children hear the love in his voice above all else;
- Dads share wisdom with their children in the hopes they spread it throughout the world;

- Thank heaven for the special relationship between fathers and daughters. It is blessed from above;

- The bond between a father and son is stronger than glue;

The father of a righteous child has great joy; a man who fathers a wise son rejoices in him.

The followings are proverbs and sayings about “father”:

- Onalik uyning ori bor, Otalik uyning — zari;

- Ota — aql, ona — idrok;

- Yaxshi qo'shni — ota-ona,

- Yomon qo'shni — boshga balo;

- O'zim hisoblasam, qulunli biya,

Otam bilan hisoblasam, bo'tali biya;

- O'roq tutib otang qolguncha,

O'ymoq tutib enag qolsin;

- Ota-bola — bir bog',

- Biri — gul, biri — bog'bon;

- Ota — xazina, aka-uka — tayanch;

- Otadoshim, otga min,

- Otasi boshqa, otdan tush.

- Otangni sog'insang, tog'angni ko'r;

- O'gay ota non bermas,

Non bersa ham, jon bermas.

- O'gay ota o'kirar,

Yuragidan bo'kirar.

Hence, if we conclude from the above mentions proverbs and sayings, in both cultures “father” is the one who loves the offsprings. Whoever pleases his parents and receives their blessings, two gates of heaven will be opened for him. And for those whose parents do not agree, two gates of hell will be opened for them.

Even if a parent oppresses a child, they will not be resisted or resisted. Because Allah said to Musa (as):

“O Moses! There is a sin that weighs as much as the mountains of the world. ”

“God! What a sin! ” Moses asked.

Allah bless you:

“When a parent or one of them calls, the child doesn't answer!”

In Uzbek culture, there are 10 rights of father which were highlighted in Hadith. In the hadiths, special attention is paid to the rights and duties of children to their parents. According to religious sources, every father has ten rights over his child. The child should do the following ten things beautifully.

1. Feeding the parents.
2. Perform services.
3. Answer "labbay" when called.
4. Obedience when commanded to do something that is not sinful.
5. Speak softly.
6. Delivery of clothes.
7. Walk behind while walking.
8. He likes what he likes for his father.
9. His father does not like what he does not like.
10. When he prays, he asks Allah for forgiveness, including his father.

He who fears the wrath of God will not offend his parents, but will somehow find a way to win their hearts, approval and prayers. Even if they are upset, the child will not stand up to them, but will look at their wishes and feelings. If they offer something wrong, wrong, or unclean, they will have to be very polite, persuasive, and warned.

Even if a parent hurts, offends, or says a harsh word, they should immediately kiss their hands, soften them, and begin to receive their prayers. Giving them presents is the best way to make them happy and happy. If the parents are elderly, they should be helped and not left alone. You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other people.

Similar commonalities can be seen in several other proverbs below. "Ota-ona o`nta farzandni boqadi, ammo o`nta farzand bitta ota-onani boqolmaydi". In English, this exemplary word is in the form of the following proverb: "One father can feed seven children, but seven children can't feed one father". It is true that parents are ready for anything for the sake of their child's development, but when children grow up, they become preoccupied with life's worries and sometimes do not know about their parents. Our parents are one of the greatest blessings given to us by God. Appreciating them in a timely manner is our first duty. In English proverbs, the invaluable wealth of a parent is interpreted as follows: "A parents are bankers provided by nature". So "Ota-ona tabiat tomonidan in'om etilgan bebaho xazinadir".

Many things in a person's life can be replaced by alternatives, and no one else can replace a parent. The following is an Uzbek and English proverb that expresses this meaning: "Har bir inson ota bo`lishi mumkin lekin hech bir inson o`zimizni otamizni o`rnini bosa olmaydi". This sentence is expressed in English as follows "Any man can be a father but it takes a special to be a dad". Respect for parents and obedience to their advice are more typical of oriental literature. Of course, it would be wrong to conclude that there is no teaching in Western literature. There are many examples of respect for parents. For example, "Listen to your father, who gave you life, do not despise your mother when she is old". That is, it means: "Senga hayot in'om etgan otangni so`zlarini tingla, onang qariganda unga g'amxo`rlik qil". The Uzbek version of the article "See your father, come down the horse" is as follows: "Otangizni ko`rsangiz otdan tushing". This proverb is used figuratively to encourage people to honor their father. Similar proverbs and sayings can be found and analyzed in many languages.

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